

World Journal on Education and Humanities Research

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Vol. 3, Issue 1, pp. 51-62

Received, December 2021; Revised January 2022;

Accepted February 2022

School Administrators Leadership Styles in the New Normal

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Abstract: The majority of administrators have difficulty identifying and implementing the most effective leadership styles in their organizations. Thus, this study evaluated the administrators' instructional and administrative leadership style and methods. As a result of these findings, this research attempts to establish the impact of instructional and administrative style leadership as a whole on teacher performance outcomes and to identify potentially helpful intermediate elements generated by certain leadership behaviors. Admins' leadership in this new normal requires more research into how they can effectively help instructors in online learning contexts, according to the data. Findings from this study also open a new research topic on school principalship, performance, and effectiveness.

Keywords: Instructional and administrative leadership, New normal setting

1. Introduction

Because of today's fast-paced developments and ever-increasing needs, educational institutions are being compelled to become more dynamic (McLoughlin & Lee, 2011; Handoyo & Anas, 2019). One of the most essential organizational structures is that of educational institutions, where both input and output are "human." Students with leadership potential will be identified, selected, and educated in schools that are arranged to suit the demands of the 21st century information age. The school administrator is a fundamental part of these organizations (Bridges, 1982; Greenfield & William, 1995; Waldron & McLeskey, 2010). For educational institutions to remain viable in the face of changing global conditions, they must have an effective management style, strong cultural texture, and strategic leadership that is consistent with the changing world.

Currently, most administrators are having difficulty finding the right leadership style to use in their administrations (Bafadal et al., 2019; Lee & Mao, 2020) This means that leaders may help clear up the uncertainty caused by the overlap of tasks in work practices, administration, and command and control at the highest levels of the

management team's work unit by implementing effective leadership practices (Sirisookslip et al., 2015). Since the majority of educational activities take place in schools, sustained leadership is of great importance (Kalkan, et al., 2020).

While the link between school leadership and student achievement has been shown in previous studies, the reality is far more complicated and unexpected (Sharma, 2018). Findings on this association aren't always clear-cut. A correlation between school leadership style and school performance has been found in several research. A principal's leadership style, according to Ubben and Hughes (1992), may help or hinder the performance of a school by fostering or restricting a productive environment for students and teachers alike. Effective school leaders, a healthy atmosphere in schools, and positive attitudes in teachers are generally seen to have a direct or indirect impact on school performance and student accomplishment (Hallinger & Heck, 1998; Kruger, Witziers, & Slegers, 2007; Witziers, Bosker, & Kruger, 2003). However, even though it appears to be a simple equation, successful school leadership and better school performance is really rather complicated and unexpected.

Leadership

There has been a shift in the responsibilities of school administrators due to the shifting nature of leadership within educational institutions. Professionalization of the principalship (Van der Westhuizen and van Vuren 2007) and a focus on creating a common vision are two ways this is reflected (Ngcobo and Tikly 2010). For the principal, this means overseeing resource allocation and assessment, as well as assuring student safety on the campus and in the building. It is necessary to have these systems in place to guarantee that teaching and learning are of the highest quality, regardless of the situation. All educators may be used to their full potential by using dispersed leadership, as we'll see in more detail below. Leadership style has also garnered great attention, in addition to an emphasis on the personal traits and jobs and activities of primary school administrators. A leader's leadership style may be defined as the line that runs through all of their actions and interactions (De Jong and Van Doorne-Huiskes 1992). A leader's leadership style is influenced by a variety of elements, including the leader's personality and prevailing set of values.

The notion of leadership is becoming more prevalent in educational literature. Leadership has been the subject of several books and articles on how to define the term, what it should include, and the consequences it has. The literature on leadership is rife with terminology, yet little agreement exists on what leadership is and how it should be practiced. Ribbins and Gunter (2002) attempted to map the area of leadership studies by comparing and contrasting the notions of administration, management, and leadership, revealing the enormity of the complexity in the subject. Vision, planning, and policymaking were once considered the first three steps in the administration process. Consequently, the terms "administration" and "management" were merged into a single concept. There are others who believe that the term "leadership" encompasses everything from policy to principles to vision. According to Richmon and Allison (2003), a quest for a clear definition of leadership is a futile endeavor since it does not exist. To this, Krüger (2010) adds his voice of agreement, noting that leadership can be understood in many ways, including as a process of influence, a process of leading and following, a personality trait, a mode of communication, a means of achieving goals, a means of establishing structure, and a means of igniting change.

Leaders, according to Msila (2011), should deliberate whether they want to function in an instructional or transformative framework. In South Africa, instructional leadership is becoming more widely accepted as a viable strategy for school reform. There has been insufficient emphasis paid to the methods through which change might be achieved, such as the requirement for modeling, monitoring, and professional communication. Through high quality classroom observation and discussion, as well as consistent standards for both student and educator conduct and practice, these may be achieved.

The study of what elements contribute to better education is an important subject of school leadership research. It has a tangential relationship to educational changes. This study topic has examined and assessed the necessity of investing in school leadership improvements. They include Elmore (1996, 2004) and Fullan (2009), as well as Harris (2009b), Harris (2009a), Louis (2007), and Hargreaves (2009, 2009; Hargreaves & Fullan; 2009; Hargreaves & Goodson; 2006; Hargreaves & Shirley, 2012). In all of their studies, they have emphasized the role of school leadership in improving education results and in the implementation of policies and reform programs. Many studies have focused on policies and their content, but not on the reform processes themselves or the surrounding contexts. As a result, several researchers have expressed concern about this gap in knowledge. There is a lack of attention to the political, historical, and long-term components of transformation in education leadership theory. A real illustration of this are the generational transformations in teachers and school leadership that have taken place over the past few decades as a result of large-scale economic and demographic changes.

Other others have been more hesitant regarding the role of school leadership in the process of change. When analyzing school culture and environment on school transformation, Lindhal (2011) found that leading reform and considerable progress might be challenging. Schools, change processes, and the leader's position are all intricately intertwined. Furthermore, there have been unreasonably high hopes for leadership development. We need to be cautious and not demand too much from school leaders and their accomplishments, as Gronn (1997) even referred to the "romantic of leadership" (p. 281).

Other studies have examined how school leaders' attempts to enhance education are affected by their leadership positions. School leadership changes can be better understood by examining the impact of school leadership on student outcomes, which is an essential part of this line of research. Many studies, conducted over the last three decades, show that strong leadership in schools is critical to improving student achievement. The impact of school leadership has been studied over the past 52 years by Hallinger (2014). 38 high-quality scientific research have been found by him that can assist assess the influence of school leadership on educational outcomes findings. Some of the most significant contributions to school leadership research and development have come from Leithwood, Seashore Louis, Anderson, and Wahlstrom (2004); Robinson et al. (2009); as well as Witziers, Bosker and Kruger (2003) in the United Kingdom, Australia, and the United States. Together, these studies show that school leadership has a statistically measurable impact on educational outcomes; that school leaders have an indirect influence; that they help create the conditions for

learning; and that there are specific leadership practices that actually help improve education outcomes.

There is no denying that educational institutions, like any other business, require capable administration and leadership. The promotion of a culture of lifelong learning and teaching is a challenge for everyone in the field of school leadership and administration (Cruz et al., 2016). Everyone has their own way of thinking about what leadership is, but according to recent research by Taylor (2020), the most universal consensus is that a good leader must have a strong grasp of interpersonal impact. There are some who are born with this capacity, and perhaps that is what sets effective leaders apart from those who are just ordinary. No school in the 180 assessed by Nannyonjo (2017) was able to increase student accomplishment records without good school leadership, according to the report. In this study, there is a definite link between effective school leadership and improved student results. Good school leadership has a direct influence on student experience and academic success, according to this study. authority, they must earn it now.

2. Purpose of the Study

Responding to these current issues and challenges pushes the researcher to conduct this study. It is inevitable that there is a divergence between school head and their subordinates, the teachers, lead to an unhealthy working environment and social stress to everyone. This study assessed the administrators in terms of instructional and administrative leadership that elevate school performance.

3. Research Methodology

This research utilized descriptive research method to gather the information about the extent is the manifestation of the practices of the school heads in terms of instructional and administrative leadership. The research environment was the selected school in the province of Cebu. Teacher and Administrators were considered in the study. Research instrument were adopted from the study of Manatad (2018), it focuses on the administrative and supervisory leadership style in relation to teaching and learning process in the school.

A transmittal letter will be prepared and address to the office of the district supervisor, requesting permission to conduct the study as the request will be approved; the researcher will start to distribute questionnaires to the administrators and teachers. Questionnaires will be retrieved and data will be collated. Data and information with regards to the study will be treated with utmost confidence.

4. Results and Discussions

Table 1. Instructional Leadership Style

Instructional Leadership Style	Teachers		Administrator	
	Mean	VD	Mean	VD
School Principals manage school operations in accordance to school's goals.	2.08	M	3	WM
School heads ensure that teacher's instruction in classroom aim to achieve goals.	2.02	M	3	WM
Principals/ school heads utilize student's performance and examination results in promoting curricular development.	2.17	M	3	WM
Principal of school heads use student's performance levels and examination results to set goals.	2.22	M	3	WM
Principals/ school heads endeavor to ensure clarity within the school about the responsibility for coordination the curriculum.	2.12	M	3	WM
Principals/School heads make sure that teachers professional development activities are aligned with school goals and curricular objectives.	2.14	M	3	WM
Principal /school heads work with teachers to address weakness and pedagogical problems	2.51	WM	3	WM
Principal/school heads solve problems with teachers when there are challenges to teaching-learning in a particular classroom.	2.41	WM	3	WM
Principals/administrators inform teachers about possibilities to update their curricular knowledge and instructional skills.	2.31	WM	3	WM
Principals/school heads make frequent suggestions to teachers on how to improve instruction in classrooms.	2.49	WM	3	WM
Grand Mean	2.25	WM	3	WM

In order to determine the perceptions of the respondents' group in terms of instructional leadership styles of the administrators, the mean results were provided in the table. As shown in table 1, the statement principal /school heads work with teachers to address weakness and pedagogical problems got the highest weighted mean of 2.51 which verbally described as well manifested. While the statement school heads ensure that teacher's instruction in classroom aim to achieve goals got the lowest weighted mean of 2.02, which verbally described as manifested. Overall, the teacher group got a final weighted mean of 2.25 which verbally described as well manifested. This indicates a positive result in terms of the instructional leadership style of the administrator. On the other hand, administrators gave an overall weighted mean of 3 which verbally described as well manifested. Principals play an important influence in determining the course of the school, according to Lynch (2015). Principals play a key role in working together with staff to set clear, quantifiable, and time-based goals for the school that ultimately lead to improved academic outcomes for students (Halinger, 2003). As a result of these results, administrators are expected to communicate and promote school-wide goals.

Table 2. Administrative Leadership Style

Administrative Leadership Style	Teachers		Administrator	
	Mean	VD	Mean	VD
Principals/school head see their role as making the school accountable internally and to stakeholders outside the school.	2.63	WM	3	WM
Principals/ school heads ensure that DepEd approved instructional approaches are explained to new teachers.	2.57	WM	3	WM
Principals/ school heads make sure that all teachers are held accountable for improving their teaching skills.	2.68	WM	3	WM
Principals/school heads focus on convincing students' parents of the need for new ideas and procedures at the school.	2.42	WM	3	WM
Principals/school heads ensure that everyone in the school follows the official rules.	2.54	WM	3	WM
Principal /school heads significantly involved in dealing with problems of scheduling of teachers and courses.	2.61	WM	3	WM
Principal / school heads ensure adequate administrative procedures in reporting to higher authorities.	2.64	WM	3	WM
Principals/ school head focus on creating an orderly and task-oriented atmosphere in the school.	2.56	WM	3	WM
Principals/school head see their role as making the school accountable internally and to stakeholders outside the school.	2.63	WM	3	WM
Principals/ school heads ensure that DepEd approved instructional approaches are explained to new teachers.	2.65	WM	3	WM
Grand Mean	2.59	WM	3	WM

Table 2 presents how both the administrators and the teachers assessed the administrative style of the school administrator. As shown in table, the statement principals/ school heads make sure that all teachers are held accountable for improving their teaching skills got the highest weighted mean of 2.68 which verbally described as well manifested. While the statement Principals/school heads focus on convincing students' parents of the need for new ideas and procedures at the school goals got the lowest weighted mean of 2.42 which verbally described as well manifested. Overall, the teacher group got a final weighted mean of 2.59 which verbally described as well manifested. This indicates a positive result in terms of the administrative leadership style of the administrator. Administrators on the other hand, gave an overall weighted mean of 3 which verbally described as well manifested in terms of administrative leadership. Administrative leadership, according to Head & Alford (2015) is the coordination of duties to grow and sustain an organization. An effective administrative leader is capable of creating systems that safeguard and sustain vital operational functions to satisfy the demands of stakeholders. Administrative leaders, on the other hand, establish purpose, encourage employees to achieve a shared vision, and ensure objectives and outcomes are met. This shows that school leaders have a high level of competence when it comes to running their prestigious institutions.

Table 3. Significant difference (Instructional Leadership)

	<i>Variable 1</i>	<i>Variable 2</i>
Mean	2.247	3
Variance	0.030268	0
Observations	10	10
Hypothesized Mean Difference	0	
df	9	
t Stat	-13.6869	
P(T<=t) one-tail	1.25E-07	
t Critical one-tail	1.833113	
P(T<=t) two-tail	2.49E-07	
t Critical two-tail	2.262157	

Table 3 shows the test significant difference between the group respondents in terms of instructional leadership. The data shows that the p- value P (T<=t) two tail (2.49E-07) gives us the probability that a value of the t-statistic (-13.6869) would be observed that it is less than in absolute value than t Critical two tail (2.26). Since the p-value is less than our alpha 0.05, hence the data reject the null hypothesis that there is no significant difference between group respondent's perception on the administrator's instructional leadership.

Table 4. Significant difference (Administrative Leadership)

	<i>Variable 1</i>	<i>Variable 2</i>
Mean	2.593	3
Variance	0.005601	0
Observations	10	10
Hypothesized Mean Difference	0	
df	9	
t Stat	-17.1972	
P(T<=t) one-tail	1.71E-08	
t Critical one-tail	1.833113	
P(T<=t) two-tail	3.42E-08	
t Critical two-tail	2.262157	

Table 4 shows the test significant difference between the group respondents in terms of administrative leadership. The data shows that the p- value P (T<=t) two tail (3.42E-08) gives us the probability that a value of the t-statistic (-17.1972) would be observed that it is less than in absolute value than t Critical two tail (2.2621). Since the p-value is less than our alpha 0.05, hence the data reject the null hypothesis that there is no significant difference between group respondent's perception on the administrator's administrative leadership.

5. Conclusion

School leaders are expected to play a pivotal role in educational systems, in which state policies regarding decentralization and accountability provide new challenges. The same applies to expectations about innovation, the improvement of quality in education and the finding of solutions for problems that arise from important changes in the

profiles and background of students entering the school. Findings shown that instructional and administrative style of leadership were manifested and this report makes up the balance about the importance of the, relatively | total effect of leadership on teacher's performance outcomes and identifies promising intermediary factors which, stimulated by specific leadership behaviors. Moreover, findings of this study open a new area of research on school principalship, performance, and effectiveness.

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